

The Availability and Adequacy, and Level of Importance of the Facilities and Services Offered by Hotel Fragaria: An Input for Partnership Program

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ABSTRACT: This study was conducted to examine, evaluate and standardize the facilities and service quality of Hotel Fragaria based on its accommodation classification to provide an avenue for the researchers to create a project proposal for an extension service and will be proposed as a related learning venue for Bachelor of Hospitality Management students' outcomes-based education program as an actual learning experience. The researchers employed both descriptive and inferential statistics in utilization in the analyses of the data. The descriptive part includes the computation of the mean to describe the level of availability and adequacy as well as the level of importance of the services and facilities of the five areas of Hotel Fragaria. The researchers made use of structured questionnaire based on the Department of Tourism National Accommodation Standards in data gathering for the in-house guests' respondents and convenience sampling was used in the data collection. The results of the study shows that "public areas" were rated the highest-level while "food and beverages" the lowest. However, regardless the observed differences, the ratings for all the listed facilities are descriptively interpreted as "available and adequate". In terms of the level of importance, all facilities are deemed "extremely important". The correlation between the level of availability and adequacy, and level of importance of such facilities and services. It can be observed that the correlation coefficient is significantly different from zero only for the case of the facilities "guestrooms" and "food and beverages." Specifically, the level of availability and adequacy is positively but weakly related to the level of importance under "guestrooms" and "food and beverages."

KEYWORDS: Level of Importance, Guest Satisfaction, Availability and Adequacy, Hotel Services, Hotel Facilities

I. INTRODUCTION

The United Nation World Tourism Organization (2013) stated that the matter of the classification of tourism accommodations is particularly difficult for at least two reasons: First, due to the large diversity of types of tourism accommodations, a diversity that is constantly increasing; and second, due to the large diversity of classification systems that are themselves embedded in highly different cultural and economic context.

In addition, hotel classification systems are widely used in the accommodation sector as a means of providing an indicator to both consumers and intermediaries on the standards to be found at individual establishments. This is particularly important in a sector where the product (i.e. the accommodation) is bought / listed sight-unseen (i.e. consumers/intermediaries are not able to see or test the product offering before the purchase / listing is made). Moreover, hotel classifications can provide useful marketing platforms for individual hotels and for destinations wishing to promote the quality of their offer.

Nevertheless, establishing a classification system for tourism accommodation is a complex undertaking due to the diversity of both accommodation types and of the cultural, environmental and economic contexts in which the systems are embedded.

The National Accommodation Standards of Hotels set by the Department of Tourism classified the five levels of accommodation standards ranging from one to five stars applicable to hotels, resorts and apartment hotels. To obtain higher stars, progressively higher service and facility quality, facility condition and improved business practices like environmental management.

Presently in the Philippines, hotel standardization and classification is done through the process of accreditation. Hotels undergo the process of accreditation conducted by the Department of Tourism. The goal is to primarily check if it would pass the

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required standards for hotel operations. The hotel standards may fall into security, hygiene, ease and expediency for hotel guests. A certificate will be issued as a proof that the property was able to meet the minimum standards and recognized by the Department of tourism.

The mandate under the Philippine Tourism Act of 2011 is to develop and implement minimum quality standards to regulate tourism activities and services countrywide and to implement criteria for classification and standardization of tourism facilities and services.

Historically, Benguet is the roof of Northern Luzon. It straddles on the Cordillera mountain ranges. Mt. Pulag, second highest mountain in the Philippines, and Halsema Highway, the highest mountain highway system in the country, are located in Benguet. Today it holds claim as the "Salad Bowl of the Philippines" because of the huge production of upland vegetables. Benguet continues to expand its commerce and industry giving emphasis to tourism. It is the most developed and fastest growing economy among the provinces of Cordillera. This owes mainly to its proximity to Baguio City and its role as seat of provincial government, educational center and trading hub of the region's vegetable industry. It currently focuses on tourism development to make it worthy of its role the tourism gateway to the Cordillera (DOT-Benguet 2016).

Hotel Fragaria was built in 2002 to cater to all guests or tourists of different classifications like business travelers, walk-ins, family, and group. It is a four (4) storey building and has 26 rooms that has standard bed with built-in cable television, and restroom inside the room, however the remaining two rooms offers matrimonial bed, with built-in cable television, and restroom inside the room. In addition, it has two function halls that can accommodate 80-100 guests approximately. With its the goal to provide quality services to clients/guests it is expected that the service quality of the hotel meets the guest's needs and expectations. It is important that the hotel comply with the local standards especially in the areas of safety, sanitation, and hygiene practices.

Thus, studies have to be conducted by the proponents to examine, evaluate and standardize the facilities and service quality of Hotel Fragaria based on its accommodation classification. This will also provide an avenue for the researchers to create a project proposal for an extension service and will be proposed as a related learning venue for Bachelor of Hospitality Management students' outcomes-based education program as an actual learning experience.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to the United Nation World Tourism Organization (2015) a Hotel classification is the ranking of hotels, usually by using nomenclature such as stars (or diamonds), with one star denoting basic facilities and standards of comfort and five stars denoting luxury in facilities and services. The purpose is to inform intending guests in advance on what can be expected in order to reduce the gap between expected and experienced facilities and service delivery. The terms 'grading', 'rating', 'classification' and 'star rating' are used to refer to the same concept, i.e. to rank hotels by their facilities and standards.

The present economic environment is marked by the deep world crisis on one hand and by the increased concern within the tourism organizations to find solutions that could sustain the economic efficiency and limit the negative effects on the other hand. Tourists' adjustment to the new economic conditions has triggered a higher interest in obtaining the best quality-price balance for the purchased tourist services, and particularly for hotel facilities. The quality of guest services offered by each supplier is the result of joining two components: quantity, which is rather of material nature as it is represented by equipment and facilities and quality, which is mainly behavioristic.

Moreover, according to Ondiek, 2015, classification is a systematic assessment of the quality standards and provision of arrange facilities and amenities in assigning symbols. It is important to observe that the diverseness of the hospitality industry also affects the classification of hotel quality. We can actually find many programmes, classifications and seals of quality promoted by public authorities and private companies that create confusion in the consumer perceptions of hotel quality. Moreover, new electronic distribution channels and their ratings are becoming a new way to gather information about a hotel and its quality. Secondly, a point that can cause complications is that different countries and regions can choose differing approaches depending on the features of the classification (number of levels, symbols used, etc.) and the nature of the programme for public and private.

In line with this, standardization is a formulation, publication, and implementation of guidelines, rules, and specifications for common and repeated use, aimed at achieving optimum degree of order or uniformity in a given, discipline or field. Standard is specific to a product or service and occupation or qualification. Thus, standards are set of specifications or descriptions of the desired state a quality or required quality level. A good example is the standard of guestroom of standard operating procedure of handling guest arrival or check-in.

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Historically, Lau et al. (2005) mentioned that the hotel classification systems were formed to ensure safe and reliable lodging and food for travelers at a time when very few such trustworthy establishments existed. The broad objectives of quality systems or standardization systems are essentially to promote quality awareness and improve performance practices and capabilities; to serve as a working tool for managing performance, planning, training and assessment; and to facilitate communication and share best practice information about successful quality strategies and benefits.

Nebes, et.al (2011) stated that several hospitality associations representing the industry support a standardized classification system even though they find it difficult to accept standards created by any non-hotelier's entity and believing that only hoteliers can understand the needs of their guests. In some countries, the national tourism boards have classifications of their own, but these differ from country to country and region to region. There is a clear need in the hospitality industry to create a universal system that is consistent and transparent.

There exists a multitude of types of official hotel classification systems across the globe, varying in terms of criteria, management and monitoring, but all essentially serving the same primary and crucial purpose of providing information on a product which is often purchased/listed sight unseen. This multiplicity of systems can nevertheless be a challenge for consumers, accommodation providers, and implementing agencies the BSU.

OBJECTIVES:

This study is to determine the availability and adequacy, and level of importance of the facilities and services offered by Hotel Fragaria.

1. Determine Hotel Fragaria's availability and adequacy of services in the following areas using the Department of Tourism's (DOT) National Accommodation Standard:

- A. Front Office (Arrival and Departure)
 - A.1. Building Appeal
 - A.2. Entrance/Exit and Parking
 - A.3. Security/Desk/Area
 - A.4. Reception Area
 - A.5. Check-in Process
- B. Guestrooms
 - B.1. Room Size (according to its classification)
 - B.2. Bed and Mattress Quality
 - B.3. Bedding and Linen Quality
 - B.4. Bedroom Lighting
 - B.5. Bedroom Amenities and Accessories
- C. Bathroom
 - C.1. Bath and shower with functioning hot and cold water
 - C.2. Bathroom basin
 - C.3. Bathroom shower curtain
 - C.4. Bathroom tiled of quality granite marble
 - C.5. Vanity mirror
 - C.6. Quality toilet bowl and seat cover
 - C.7. Available towels of good quality
 - C.8. Available toilet amenities
- D. Food and Beverage
 - D.1. Available restaurant or coffee shop
- E. Public Areas
 - E.1. Function rooms
 - E.2. Public toilet with wash area
 - E.3. Emergency and Fire exit evacuation
 - E.4. Business center (Photocopier, souvenir shop)

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2. Determine Hotel Fragaria's services' level of importance in the following areas using the Department of Tourism's (DOT) National Accommodation Standard:

- A. Front Office (Arrival and Departure)
 - A.1. Building Appeal
 - A.2. Entrance/Exit and Parking
 - A.3. Security/Desk/Area
 - A.4. Reception Area
 - A.5. Check-in Process
- B. Guestrooms
 - B.1. Room Size (according to its classification)
 - B.2. Bed and Mattress Quality
 - B.3. Bedding and Linen Quality
 - B.4. Bedroom Lighting
 - B.5. Bedroom Amenities and Accessories
- C. Bathroom
 - C.1. Bath and shower with functioning hot and cold water
 - C.2. Bathroom basin
 - C.3. Bathroom shower curtain
 - C.4. Bathroom tiled of quality granite marble
 - C.5. Vanity mirror
 - C.6. Quality toilet bowl and seat cover
 - C.7. Available towels of good quality
 - C.8. Available toilet amenities
- D. Food and Beverage
 - D.1. Available restaurant or coffee shop
- E. Public Areas
 - E.1. Function rooms
 - E.2. Public toilet with wash area
 - E.3. Emergency and Fire exit evacuation
 - E.4. Business center (Photocopier, souvenir shop)

3. Identify the significant relationship between the availability and adequacy of Hotel Fragaria's Services' and level of importance.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This presents the methods that were used in this study together with procedures employed in the construction and validation of the questionnaire. The researches employed both descriptive and inferential statistics in utilization in the analyses of the data. The descriptive part includes the computation of the mean to describe the level of availability and adequacy as well as the level of importance of the services and facilities of the five areas of Hotel Fragaria. The questionnaire was formulated based on the Department of Tourism (DOT) National Accommodation Standard tool for the in-house respondents' as basis for improving the facilities and services.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The following concepts and their context were considered in formulating the research paradigm for this study. The relationship of the input-process-output considered by this study is illustrated in Figure 1.

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Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS

The researchers made use of structured-questionnaire based on the Department of Tourism National Accommodation Standards in data gathering for the in-house guests’ respondents. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part one consisted of the guided response type particularly the recall type. It supplied the following information about their demographic profile: age, height, weight, civil status, gender, ethnicity and occupation. The respondents were given instructions to write/use a check mark on their appropriate answer.

The second part of the questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part consisted the availability and adequacy of facilities and services, and the second part is the level of importance of the facilities and services. The respondents were given instructions to write the rating equivalent to the availability and adequacy, and level of importance of facilities and services offered by Hotel Fragaria.

The following rating scale was used for the Availability and Adequacy

Rating Scale	Description
1	Not Available
2	Available and Fairly Adequate
3	Available and Adequate
4	Available and Very Adequate

The following rating scale will be used for the Level of Importance:

Rating Scale	Description
1	Not Important
2	Slightly Importance
3	Moderately Important

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4	Very Important
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Data Collection Procedure

The two questionnaires were constructed based on the Department of Tourism National Accommodation Standards and were designed to help the researchers determine whether the facilities and services offered by Hotel Fragaria's qualifies as a major criterion in standardizing its facilities and services. The researchers personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents to ensure that the instructions for responding to the questionnaire are made clear.

The data gathered were sorted, tallied and tabulated by sets and variables related to the specific problems of the study. Convenience sampling was used in the data collection. Convenience sampling is also known as *availability sampling*, it is a specific type of non-probability *sampling* method that relies on data collection from population members who are conveniently available to participate in study and proximity to the researcher/s.

TREATMENT OF DATA

The data on the questionnaire were subjected to statistical treatment using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson's r) to measure the strength of the relationship between the variables. The inferential portion however is the testing of the hypothesis that the correlation coefficient is not significantly different from zero.

The formula used is as follows:

The mean \bar{x} is given by

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_i^n x_i}{n} \text{ where}$$

x_i : i^{th} observation
 n : sample size.

Pearson's r on the other hand is computed using the formula

$$r = \frac{\sum XY - \frac{(\sum X)(\sum Y)}{n}}{\sqrt{(\sum Y^2 - \frac{(\sum Y)^2}{n})(\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{n})}}$$

Where:

n : Number of cases

X : Average Mathematics grades of the respondents

Y : Level of problem-solving success of the respondents

$\sum X$: Summation of the average Mathematics grades

$\sum Y$: Summation of the level of problem-solving success

$\sum x^2$: Summation of the squares of average Mathematics grades

$\sum Y^2$: Summation of the squares of the level of problem-solving success

$(\sum X)^2$: Squared summation of the average Mathematics grades

$(\sum Y)^2$: Squared summation of the level of problem-solving success

The significance of the correlation coefficient was tested using t-test at 5% level of significance. The formula for t-test is given by:

$$r = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

Where:

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r : Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

n : number of cases

The strength of the relationship is based on the following ranges of the correlation coefficient:

Ranges of r	Degree/Strength of Relationship
1	Perfect Relationship
0.80 to 0.99	Very Strong/ Very High
0.60 to 0.79	Strong/High
0.40 to 0.59	Moderate/ Substantial
0.20 to 0.39	Weak/Small
0.01 to 0.19	Almost negligible/Very Weak
0	No correlation

The responses of the respondents were similarly processed in order to establish the availability and adequacy, and level of importance of the facilities and services offered by Hotel Framagia.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This chapter of the study presents the pertinent data relative to the specific problems of the study. There are 50 in-house guests' respondents in answering the questionnaire.

Front Office

Table 1. Front Office level of availability and adequacy, and level of importance of the facilities and services offered by the Hotel Framagia's, as well as the correlation between these levels

CRITERIA	MEAN LEVEL OF AVAILABILITY AND ADEQUACY			MEAN LEVEL OF IMPORTANCE			PEARSON'S r		P-VALUE
	DE	RANK		DE	RANK		DE		
Building Appearance	3.09	AA	3	3.71	EI	3	0.16 ^{ns}	VW	0.26
Building Design and Construction Quality	2.96	AA	5	3.68	EI	6	0.12 ^{ns}	VW	0.41
Building Condition	2.76	AA	8	3.74	EI	2	0.18 ^{ns}	VW	0.20
Entrance/Exit and Parking	2.95	AA	6	3.66	EI	7	0.04 ^{ns}	VW	0.77
Security Desk/Area	3.39	AA	1	3.77	EI	1	0.22 ^{ns}	W	0.12
Reception Area	3.07	AA	4	3.69	EI	5	0.08 ^{ns}	VW	0.57
Check-In Process	2.92	AA	7	3.64	EI	8	0.20 ^{ns}	W	0.17
Check-Out Process	3.24	AA	2	3.70	EI	4	0.18 ^{ns}	VW	0.22
FRONT OFFICE	3.05	AA		3.70	EI		-0.18 ^{ns}	VW	0.21

Legend

	Level of Availability and Adequacy	Level of Importance	Ranges of r	Strength of Relationship
1.00-1.49	Not Available (NA)	Not Important (NI)	1.00	Perfect Relationship (P)
1.50-2.49	Available and Fairly Adequate (AFA)	Slightly Important (SI)	0.80 to 0.99	Very Strong (VS)
2.50-3.49	Available and Adequate (AA)	Moderately Important (MI)	0.60 to 0.79	Strong (S)
3.50-4.00	Available and Very Adequate (AVA)	Extremely Important (EI)	0.40 to 0.59	Moderate (M)
ns	Not significant		0.20 to 0.39	Weak (W)
*	Significant		0.01 to 0.19	Very Weak (VW)
**	Highly significant		0.00	No correlation (NC)

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Presented in table 1 are the results for the front office. All criteria are rated “available and adequate” and “extremely important.” Of the listed criteria, “security/desk area” and “check-out processes” garnered the highest mean level for availability and adequacy while “building conditions” the lowest. Similarly, “security/desk area” and “building conditions” were graded the most important while “check-in processes” the least. Since the p-values are all greater than 0.05, this indicate that the correlation coefficients are all not significantly different from zero.

Guestrooms

Table 2. Guestroom level of availability and adequacy, and level of importance of the facilities and services offered by the Hotel Fragaria, as well as the correlation between these levels

CRITERIA	MEAN LEVEL OF AVAILABILITY AND ADEQUACY	DE	RANK	MEAN LEVEL OF IMPORTANCE	DE	RANK	PEARSON'S r	DE	P-VALUE
Room Size	3.20	AA	1	3.74	EI	1.5	0.15 ^{ns}	VW	0.29
Bed Mattress Quality	3.05	AA	2	3.72	EI	3	0.23 ^{ns}	W	0.11
Bedding and Linen Quality	2.86	AA	3	3.74	EI	1.5	0.18 ^{ns}	VW	0.22
Bedroom Lighting	2.80	AA	5	3.69	EI	4	0.31*	W	0.03
Bedroom Furniture	2.82	AA	4	3.65	EI	6	0.38**	W	0.01
Bedroom Amenities and Accessories	2.50	AA	6	3.68	EI	5	0.15 ^{ns}	VW	0.30
OVERALL	2.87	AA		3.77	EI		0.31*	W	0.03

Legend

	Level of Availability and Adequacy	Level of Importance	Ranges of r	Strength of Relationship
1.00-	Not Available (NA)	Not Important (NI)	1.00	Perfect Relationship (P)
1.49	Available and Fairly Adequate (AFA)	Slightly Important (SI)	0.80 to 0.99	Very Strong (VS)
1.50-		Moderately Important (MI)	0.60 to 0.79	Strong (S)
2.49	Available and Adequate (AA)		0.40 to 0.59	Moderate (M)
2.50-	Available and Very Adequate (AVA)	Extremely Important (EI)	0.20 to 0.39	Weak (W)
3.49			0.01 to 0.19	Very Weak (VW)
3.50-	Not significant		0.00	No correlation (NC)
4.00	Significant			
ns	Highly significant			
*				
**				

Table 2 on the other hand displays the respondents’ rating on the different dimensions of the guestrooms. Evidently, all criteria are “available and adequate” and are “extremely important.” Moreover, the correlation coefficient is significantly different from zero under “bedroom lighting” and is highly significant under “bedroom furniture.” These coefficients are both positive and weak suggesting that a slight change on the level of availability and adequacy results to an occasional change in the level of importance in vice versa.

Bathrooms

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Table 3. Bathroom level of availability and adequacy, and level of importance of the facilities and services offered by the Hotel Fragaria, as well as the correlation between these levels

CRITERIA	MEAN LEVEL OF AVAILABILITY AND ADEQUACY			MEAN LEVEL OF IMPORTANCE			PEARSON'S r	DE	P-VALUE
	DE	RANK		DE	RANK				
Bath and Shower with Functioning Hot and Cold Water	2.82	AA	5	3.78	EI	1	0.05 ^{ns}	VW	0.73
Bathroom Basin	2.80	AA	6.5	3.62	EI	7.5	0.14 ^{ns}	VW	0.34
Bathroom Shower Curtain	2.84	AA	4	3.70	EI	3	0.11 ^{ns}	VW	0.43
Bathroom tiled with Quality Granite or Marble	2.96	AA	2	3.68	EI	4.5	0.38 ^{**}	W	0.01
Vanity Mirror	2.80	AA	6.5	3.66	EI	6	0.46 ^{**}	M	0.00
Quality Toilet Bowl with Seat and Cover	3.00	AA	1	3.72	EI	2	0.16 ^{ns}	VW	0.26
Available Towels of Good Quality	2.86	AA	3	3.68	EI	4.5	0.14 ^{ns}	VW	0.33
Available Toilet Amenities	2.54	AA	8	3.62	EI	7.5	0.08 ^{ns}	VW	0.57
OVERALL	2.83	AA		3.68	EI		0.13 ^{ns}	VW	0.37

Legend

	Level of Availability and Adequacy	Level of Importance	Ranges of r	Strength of Relationship
1.00-1.49	Not Available (NA)	Not Important (NI)	1.00	Perfect Relationship (P)
1.50-2.49	Available and Fairly Adequate (AFA)	Slightly Important (SI)	0.80 to 0.99	Very Strong (VS)
2.50-3.49	Available and Adequate (AA)	Moderately Important (MI)	0.60 to 0.79	Strong (S)
3.50-4.00	Available and Very Adequate (AVA)	Extremely Important (EI)	0.40 to 0.59	Moderate (M)
ns	Not significant		0.20 to 0.39	Weak (W)
*	Significant		0.01 to 0.19	Very Weak (VW)
**	Highly significant		0.00	No correlation (NC)

Similar results on the level of availability and adequacy, and level of importance of the bathroom facilities and services are observed. Furthermore, the two variables had their highest and significant correlation under "vanity mirror" and "tiling" while not significantly different from zero elsewhere. These results are given in table 3.

Food and Beverage

Table 4. Food and Beverage level of availability and adequacy, and level of importance of the facilities and services offered by the Hotel Fragaria, as well as the correlation between these levels

CRITERIA	MEAN LEVEL OF AVAILABILITY AND ADEQUACY			MEAN LEVEL OF IMPORTANCE			PEARSON'S r	DE	P-VALUE
	DE	RANK		DE	RANK				
Available restaurant or coffee shop	2.58	AA		3.60	EI		0.33 [*]	W	0.02
OVERALL	2.58	AA		3.60	EI		0.33 [*]	W	0.02

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Legend				
	Level of Availability and Adequacy	Level of Importance	Ranges of r	Strength of Relationship
1.00-1.49	Not Available (NA)	Not Important (NI)	1.00	Perfect Relationship (P)
1.50-2.49	Available and Fairly Adequate (AFA)	Slightly Important (SI)	0.80 to 0.99	Very Strong (VS)
2.50-3.49	Available and Adequate (AA)	Moderately Important (MI)	0.60 to 0.79	Strong (S)
3.50-4.00	Available and Very Adequate (AVA)	Extremely Important (EI)	0.40 to 0.59	Moderate (M)
ns	Not significant		0.20 to 0.39	Weak (W)
*	Significant		0.01 to 0.19	Very Weak (VW)
**	Highly significant		0.00	No correlation (NC)

Table 4 presented the level of availability, adequacy, and importance of the facilities under “food and beverage.” Results reveal that the availability of restaurant and coffee shop is adequate and available, and it is extremely important.

Public Area

Table 5. Public area level of availability and adequacy, and level of importance of the facilities and services offered by the Hotel Fragaria, as well as the correlation between these levels

CRITERIA	MEAN LEVEL OF AVAILABILITY AND ADEQUACY			MEAN LEVEL OF IMPORTANCE			PEARSON'S r	DE	P-VALUE
	DE	RANK		DE	RANK				
Function Rooms	3.06	AA	3	3.80	EI	3	0.21 ^{ns}	W	0.15
Public Toilet with Wash Area	3.28	AA	1	3.86	EI	2	0.38 ^{**}	W	0.01
Emergency and Fire Exit Evacuation	3.24	AA	2	3.92	EI	1	0.10 ^{ns}	VW	0.51
Business Centers	2.64	AA	4	3.72	EI	4	0.28 [*]	W	0.05
OVERALL	3.06	AA		3.83	EI		0.18 ^{ns}	VW	0.22

Legend				
	Level of Availability and Adequacy	Level of Importance	Ranges of r	Strength of Relationship
1.00-1.49	Not Available (NA)	Not Important (NI)	1.00	Perfect Relationship (P)
1.50-2.49	Available and Fairly Adequate (AFA)	Slightly Important (SI)	0.80 to 0.99	Very Strong (VS)
2.50-3.49	Available and Adequate (AA)	Moderately Important (MI)	0.60 to 0.79	Strong (S)
3.50-4.00	Available and Very Adequate (AVA)	Extremely Important (EI)	0.40 to 0.59	Moderate (M)
ns	Not significant		0.20 to 0.39	Weak (W)
*	Significant		0.01 to 0.19	Very Weak (VW)
**	Highly significant		0.00	No correlation (NC)

Table 5 is concerned with the level of availability, adequacy, and importance of the facilities under “public area.” Results reveal that “public toilets” and “emergency and fire exists” are the most available, adequate, and important while “function rooms” and “business centers” the least. Moreover, a significant and positive but weak correlation is observed under “public toilets” and “emergency and fire exist.”

CONCLUSION

Based on the foregoing it can be concluded that most of the guests’ respondents presents the mean level of availability and adequacy of the identified facilities and services offered by the Hotel Fragaria. Results reveal that “public areas” were rated the highest-level while “food and beverages” the lowest. However, regardless the observed differences, the ratings for all the listed

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facilities are descriptively interpreted as “available and adequate” since the mean is within the interval “2.50-3.49”. In terms of the level of importance, all facilities are deemed “extremely important” as indicated by their corresponding mean all greater than 3.50.

The correlation between the level of availability and adequacy, and level of importance of such facilities and services. It can be observed that the correlation coefficient is significantly different from zero only for the case of the facilities “guestrooms” and “food and beverages.” Specifically, the level of availability and adequacy is positively but weakly related to the level of importance under “guestrooms” and “food and beverages.”

This further means that whenever there is an increase/decrease in the level of availability and adequacy, a slight or occasional increase/decrease is observed in the level of importance in vice versa.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers deemed it proper to recommend the following:

1. Provide a visible design and layout of the frontage and public area that includes function hall and parking area.
2. Provide room service for in-house guests
3. To standardize the facilities and services of Hotel Fragaria based on its classification.
4. Create Standard Operating Procedures for Hotel Fragaria facilities and services for standardization based on the Department of Tourism National Accommodation Standards.
5. This might be an additional reference to the future researchers that might be conducted related to this topic.

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REFERENCES

1. Adepoju, D. 2014. Standardization and Classification in the Lagos Hospitality Industry.
2. A, A. 2006. Automobile Association. Retrieved 10 18, 2007, from: [www.theaa.com staticdocs/pdf/travelandleisure/hotels/quality_standards_for_hotels.pdf](http://www.theaa.com/staticdocs/pdf/travelandleisure/hotels/quality_standards_for_hotels.pdf).
3. Bushwell, W. 2003. Service quality in Leisure and Tourism. Cambridge, USA:CABI publishing.
4. Chevalier, J. 2004. The Social Analysis System. Carlton University, Ottawa,Canada.
5. Chon, K. S. K. & Sparrowe, R. T. 2000. Hospitality an Introduction 2nd edition.USA: Delmar Thomson Learning.
6. Department of Tourism National Accommodation Standards
7. Fors, R.C., Sturman, M. C., and Heaten C.P. 2012. Total Quality Management for Hospitality and Tourism.Cengage Learning Asia Pte.Ltd.
8. Kiplagat, W, Makindi, S. and Obate, G. 2015. An Analysis of Hotel rating and Its Implications on Financial Turnover of rated Hotels in Kenya.International Journal of Environment, Vol. 5.
9. Kunzany N. and Chaisawat, M. 2011. Guidelines for Standardization and Classification of Hotels in Bhutan. Journal of Tourism Hospitality and Culture Arts Vol. 3, Issue 2.
10. Ondiek, W. 2015. Standardization and Classification: A Tool for Enhancing Destination Competitiveness and Sustainability. Standards, Workforce Development & Training Accreditation Management
11. <http://www2.unwto.org/agora/about-hotel-classification-systems>
12. https://static.hosteltur.com/web/uploads/2015/03/OMT_clasificaciyn_hotelera_4y5estrellas.pdf
<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/6283818.pdf>